

Surgical Factors Associated with Unplanned Intubations

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Background

Unplanned intubations (UIs)

- Circumstances requiring an unanticipated advanced airway with ventilatory support - intraoperatively or within 30 days after surgery
- UIs occur at a rate of 3%, the associated mortality rate ranges from 31-71%
- UIs cost US healthcare system an estimated \$1.96 billion dollars annually

Problem

- Gap in knowledge between surgical factors and UIs

National Surgical Quality Improvement Program (NSQIP)

- Database that provides clinical information used for research and quality improvement
- Perform a secondary data analysis from NSQIP database to find correlations

Literature Review

- **Five Themes:** Anesthesia type, length of surgery, surgical blood loss, type of surgery (cardiothoracic, neurosurgery, and head and neck [ENT]), and/or emergent nature of surgery have high associations with UIs

Purpose and Aims

Purpose

- Conduct a comprehensive review of literature to assess the association of surgical factors and UIs
- Identify surgical factors associated with UIs within the perioperative hospital setting

Aim

- Provide a secondary analysis of the NSQIP dataset to elicit correlations between surgical factors and UIs
- Provide recommendations to anesthesia providers and increase patient safety
- Develop a publishable manuscript

Methods

- **Design:** Retrospective cohort study
- **Sample:** Surgical patients from NSQIP dataset from years 2017 to 2019

Results

Key Takeaways

- Positively correlated with UIs:
 - Perioperative bleeding/transfusions
 - Long operative times
 - Postoperative return to OR
- Negatively correlated with UIs:
 - MAC/IV sedation and Spinal Anesthesia
 - Elective surgeries

Cardiac

¹Covariate Wald p-value; ²Covariate Wald p-value.

Thoracic

¹Covariate Wald p-value; ²Covariate Wald p-value.

Neurosurgery

¹Covariate Wald p-value; ²Covariate Wald p-value.

ENT

¹Covariate Wald p-value; ²Covariate Wald p-value.

Instrument and Analysis

Instrument

- NSQIP Dataset from 2017 to 2019

Analysis

- Descriptive statistics (univariate analysis, multivariate logistic regression, Chi-Square and Kruskal-Wallis test) used to describe characteristics and categorical variables

Challenges and Limitations

- NSQIP dataset only collects data from participating hospitals, is not generalizable for all surgeries or institutions
- Data mining was limited to the years 2017 to 2019 and does not include current data due to the COVID-19 virus
- This study only focused on cardiac, thoracic, neurosurgery, and ENT surgeries and does not provide data from other specialties

Discussion

Key Components

- Monitored anesthesia care (MAC)/ Intravenous (IV) sedation, and spinal anesthesia were less likely to result in UIs
- Increased length of surgery (OPTIME) by one hour from planned length increased odds of UIs
- Return to OR (RETURNOR) had the strongest correlation to UI with a 4-fold increased odds
- Increased surgical blood loss perioperative transfusions (OTHBLEED) increase 80-94% odds of UI linked to respiratory compromise
- All surgical specialties also supported increased OPTIME, OTHBLEED and RETURNOR with higher occurrences of UIs
- Elective surgeries (ELECTSURG) were negatively correlated with UIs

Recommendations

- Include current data from the NSQIP database and expand on more surgical specialties
- Further examine the specifics of OPTIME and OTHBLEED where UIs tend to occur
- Develop clinical decision-support tool